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Trust conditions and privacy perceptions in the use of accepted ambient technologies for health-related purposes

Wiktoria Wilkowska, Sophia Otten, Caterina Maidhof and Martina Ziefle

Chair of Communication Science, Human-Computer Interaction Center, RWTH Aachen University, Germany

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ABSTRACT

Consequences of an aging society pose one of the major challenges of our time. Technology solutions that alleviate the strain on the overburdened healthcare system can effectively support persons needing assistance. Still, technology acceptance is a key variable in understanding what drives users to utilize such applications. This study examined the role of trust and privacy in the accepted use of ambient technologies for health-related purposes. Using an online survey we collected data from $N=102$ respondents. Findings revealed that participants are willing to use ambient technology for health. Benefits and barriers are traded off, whereby the advantages outweigh the perceived barriers. Trust conditions to be fulfilled include data security, technical soundness, and health-related aspects. Having control over personal information results as the most important privacy aspect, followed by the supervision of social contacts. Regression analyses revealed perceived motives and barriers, technical soundness, and health-related trust to be significant predictors of acceptance.

KEYWORDS

Ambient technology; technology acceptance; trust; privacy; health

1. Introduction

Demographic change and its consequences for older individuals and those in poor health have posed considerable challenges to the healthcare system. On the one hand, the population's life expectancy is growing steadily, on the other hand, this development is accompanied by falling birth rates. This so-called Third Demographic Transition describes a phenomenon that consists of falling female fertility, improved early childhood survival, extended longevity, and the rapid growth in the proportion of the elderly population in a society (Ogura & Jakovljevic, 2018). At the same time, the families undergo significant changes in their social role changing from large or multi-generation families to nuclear families that lose most of the functions for production and intergenerational resource transmission (Jakovljevic & Getzen, 2016).

In Germany, the increasing aging of the society has already caused far-reaching consequences in healthcare and the economy: The changing age structure of the population leads to a higher number of old-age diseases and an increase in multimorbidity, i.e., the presence of at least two chronic conditions. The multimorbidity is, in turn, related

to a higher risk of care dependency (Koller, 2014) and causes further expenditures. In addition, the resulting high healthcare costs are aggravated by a declining number of working contributors (Wübker, 2018) and, on the side of the service providers in the nursing sector, current demographic developments are exacerbating the bottleneck regarding the next generation of medical and nursing specialists (Kuntosch, 2022).

On the other side, the consequences of an aging population can be at least partially offset by technological innovations. Emerging technologies such as big data, cloud computing, and blockchain are revolutionizing healthcare operations and delivery (Dhagarra, 2020; Ekblaw et al., 2016; Gan et al., 2015; Yang, 2015). Today's technologies are no longer tied to a specific location and enable assistance regardless of where people are. They have long since reached young individuals and those who did not grow up with rapid technological developments. But how can technology solutions effectively support persons needing assistance? Older persons and individuals with frail health can significantly profit from specialized or assistive technologies tailored to their health-related needs. Given the potential of the technology, users can benefit from the manifold technical functions in their private settings by generally improving their health-related safety, maintaining their physical well-being, optimizing their everyday routines, and maintaining their mobility. In addition to applications that monitor vital parameters, physical activities, or daily habits, older and frail persons can also use age- or illness-specialized functions. There is a multitude of disease-specific mHealth or sensor-based applications, for instance, for persons with congenital heart disease (e.g., Cedars & Blackmore, 2019), respiratory diseases (e.g., Hashoul & Haick, 2019), sleep disorders (e.g., Penzel et al., 2018), and predominantly older individuals exclusive health conditions such as Alzheimer's disease or dementia (e.g., Pappadà et al., 2021; Ienca et al., 2017). Long-term analyses of such health-related data enable early identification of deviations from usual vital values or normal behaviors and the detection of possible abnormalities in different physical functions, providing security for the users and their relatives in everyday life. Thus, research and development in the domain of information technologies open up possibilities in a wide variety of application contexts. Wearable/mobile as well as ambient/stationary technologies that use the Internet of Things (IoT), lifelogging, and increasingly artificial intelligence to provide the best possible services in different areas of life are capable of assisting the users in their home environments (smart homes or Ambient Assisted Living facilities) in a precisely targeted manner in terms of their requirements and needs (Gan et al., 2015; Rashidi & Mihailidis, 2013). Within healthcare *ambient technology* opens up far-reaching opportunities for prevention, treatment medicine, diagnostics, and rehabilitation measures, but also for healthy living and behavioral habits, allowing at the same time for reduction, or at least a better control, of health-related expenditures.

Apart from the associated costs, the use of such ambient technologies and systems is not guaranteed by the mere fact that they exist. The adoption and effective use of this technology depends on many factors and is linked to various conditions (Agarwal et al., 2010; Jaschinski, 2018); all the more in a user group that does not have an intrinsic affinity for technology systems, such as the older technology generations (Chang & Oestlund, 2019; Ivan et al., 2020; Lorenz et al., 2009; Maidhof et al., 2022; Sackmann & Winkler, 2013; Ziefle & Bay, 2005). Acceptance research has repeatedly confirmed that the perceived benefits and barriers of the technology, as well as its perceived usefulness, have a significant influence on the willingness to use it (Jaschinski & Allouch, 2015; Peek et al., 2014; Yusif et al., 2016; Zander et al., 2021). In addition, privacy and the perception of it have been a prominent topic in recent years and a *sine qua non* for smooth technology adoption (e.g., Lorenzen et al., 2011; Mihailidis & Colonna, 2020;

Wilkowska et al., 2022; Yusif et al., 2016). Not least, trust in this technology—its reliability and accuracy—is one of the key requirements, especially if it is to support a person’s highest good: health (Montague et al., 2009; Wilkowska & Ziefle, 2019). Even though these issues are not new in scientific research on technology adoption, these aspects and their interrelations are hardly considered together in the context of technology acceptance. In our empirical study, we combine all these aspects and aim for demonstrating how trust conditions and general privacy perceptions are related to the ambient technology’s acceptance. In the following, we go into more detail about the individual constructs and present later our methodological approach and the results of the study.

2. Theoretical Background and Hypotheses

In this section, the current state of the research field is reviewed referring to technology acceptance and the concepts of trust and privacy in the context of ambient technology.

2.1. *Technology acceptance in the context of ambient technologies*

To reach wide use of technology, such as ambient technologies, its acceptance among potential users is a decisive requirement. This has led to an extensive body of literature proposing measurements and models of technology acceptance. Traditionally, the Technology Acceptance Model (TAM) (Davis, 1989) and the Unified Theory of Acceptance and Use of Technology (UTAUT) (Venkatesh et al., 2003) persist in research on the construct. The main variables of these robust and established models are Perceived Usefulness (PU) and Perceived Ease of Use (PEOU) which have been shown to explain 40—70% of an individual’s intention to use technology in several contexts including healthcare. Throughout the years, several extensions of these models have been proposed, which have been included in various user studies aiming to understand the conditions and dynamics under which (potential) users may adopt a certain technology (for an overview see Davis et al., 2020).

Regarding user studies on ambient technology, studies have reported a rather positive trend towards accepting ambient devices (Peek et al., 2014) mentioning that the specific applications are perceived as helpful, beneficial, and providing an increased sense of safety and security as well as greater independence (Garg et al., 2014; Govercin et al., 2010; Wild et al., 2008). These aspects are all among the benefits or motives of using ambient technology and are usually weeded out with the barriers of such adoption (Offermann-van Heek & Ziefle, 2019; Schomakers & Ziefle, 2022). The most important barrier in the ambient domain is privacy concerns which comprise a fear of data misuse and continuous surveillance. A further barrier concerns the fear of losing personal human contact (Jaschinski & Allouch, 2015; Peek et al., 2014).

Besides the strength of pro- and counter-arguments of using ambient devices, personal circumstances among users play a crucial role in technology acceptance (Lorenzen et al., 2011; Peek et al., 2014; Yusif et al., 2016). Indeed, user diversity, including gender, age, health condition, and care needs, but also the disposition to trust (technology) considerably influence how the single benefits and barriers are evaluated and weighted in the trade-off process of acceptance (Offermann-van Heek & Ziefle, 2019; Offermann-van Heek et al., 2019; Schomakers & Ziefle, 2022). For instance, care-experienced individuals rely more on emotional aspects when deciding for or against assistive technology use compared to individuals who have never cared for another

person (Offermann-van Heek & Ziefle, 2019). A qualitative study researching mental models of assistive technology use (Maidhof et al., 2022) reported that the oldest participants (at age of 81 years) were least capable to grasp the complexity of factors playing a role in healthcare support from ambient technology, but they were also the most accepting participants, who mentioned fewer privacy concerns and showed more signs of trust in the system than younger and more technology-savvy participants. With an exploratory approach, Schomakers et al. (2020) investigated the interplay between privacy and trust in smart homes and reported that the perceptions of privacy and trust are made based on a risk evaluation and influence each other. In more detail, the authors observed that trust in data protection (one major privacy aspect) significantly influences perceived privacy in a smart home, which in turn influences technological risks (e.g., how securely is data stored, who can access data) that are dependent on trust perceptions. In a subsequent study, Schomakers et al. (2021) quantified the interplay between these concepts underlining that trust as well as privacy are highly relevant in the decision-making process of using smart homes.

Trust and privacy are both multi-dimensional constructs that can be conceptualized and measured either as more specific or on a general level. When studying trust and privacy together, conceptualizations and measurement levels should be precise. From the literature it is known that trust and privacy are very interrelated concepts (Schomakers et al., 2020, 2021) and both concepts can be considered important factors when potential users decide for or against ambient technology usage. Regarding the context of ambient assisted living (AAL) technology targeted at older adults and their health-related concerns, these two constructs have oftentimes been studied separately and the influence of these two constructs on technology acceptance and their interrelations among each other have not been looked at extensively so far (Liao et al., 2019; Schomakers & Ziefle, 2022; Wilkowska & Ziefle, 2012).

2.2. The concept of trust when using ambient technologies

Throughout the research, trust has always been considered diffuse and hard to grasp. It is a multidisciplinary construct by nature as it pertains to the most evolutionary affective states of humans but is needed in any single interaction and decision (Ross & LaCroix, 1996). Researchers have tried to define, integrate, and connect trust in various situations but it still remains hard to grasp. Most commonly, it is defined as a belief or an expectancy (Harrison et al., 2001; Krueger & Meyer-Lindenberg, 2019). In most contexts, there is a *trustor*, i.e., the person giving the trust, and a *trustee*, i.e., the person that is trusted. In the recent past, the trustee can also be a non-human object, often a technology of some sort. This can be an e-vendor, applications like Facebook and Twitter, but also intelligent systems, including ambient technologies (Jacovi & Marasovic, 2021; Ryan, 2020). Within the literature on human-automation interaction, trust can be defined as "the attitude that an agent will help achieve an individual's goals in a situation characterized by uncertainty and vulnerability" (Lee & See, 2004, p. 54). Trust is a crucial component when investigating ambient technologies, such as AAL technologies. It has been shown to be a significant predictor of technology acceptance as well as the behavioral intention to use technologies (Hoff & Bashir, 2015; Steinke et al., 2014). Like in other research fields, trust in AAL is dependent on multiple factors, relating to the technology itself, the potential users, and the context it is introduced to (Brell et al., 2019; Otten & Ziefle, 2022). Of the technology-related factors, reliability and data security have the biggest impact on trust evaluations

while user-related factors include previous experience with (medical) technology, trust disposition, health status, age, and care requirements (Steinke et al., 2014). Other situational factors, such as patient-physician relationship, information transparency, and living situation play a role as well (Xu et al., 2014). In acceptance and privacy research, more emphasis is put on the requirements for the technology itself, while trust is heavily related to human interactions behind the technology. This means that trust in ambient technology is formed based on attributes of the technology, but also on whether or not trusted persons (such as the primary care physician) recommend it or if they can operate it well (Qiao et al., 2015). Overall, trust is both a predictor and mediating variable between perceived benefits and barriers, later acceptance of ambient technologies. At the same time, it is directly and indirectly influenced by a complex network of variables, which suggests an intricate web of factors that need to be investigated in understanding trust in ambient technologies and its influence on both privacy perceptions and acceptance. It is therefore crucial to investigate trust together with other variables related to ambient technologies, such as privacy.

2.3. Privacy perceptions in general

Conceptualizations of privacy in attitudinal and behavioral research often coin privacy as a state of mind (Alpert, 2003; Westin, 1967), an assertion of control (Goodwin, 1991; Milne, 2000; Westin, 1967) or a personality trait (i.e., disposition to privacy) (Li, 2014) with always having a component of how privacy is reached and a component of why privacy is aimed at (Altman, 1974; Pedersen, 1997, 1999). In line with this, Margulis (1977) named selective control mechanisms to describe the accomplishment of privacy (*how*) and the reasons of autonomy and decrease of vulnerability as the main goals of privacy pursuit (*why*). Thereby, the privacy construct can be subdivided into several dimensions (Burgoon, 1982; Marshall, 1974). The most prominent dimension is *information privacy* (Burgoon et al., 1989; Decrew, 1997; Smith et al., 2011) regarding personal data and information. Other dimensions are *social privacy* (i.e., control over social contacts comprising the extent and nature of interactions with others), *physical privacy* (i.e., control over personal space, aspects of crowding, and being touched by others) and *psychological privacy*, (i.e., identity, thoughts and feelings, and the control over these (Burgoon et al., 1989; Burgoon, 1982; Goffman, 1972; Klopfer & Rubenstein, 1977; Laufer & Wolfe, 1977; Pastalan, 1970).

In research on ambient technologies privacy is labeled as one of the most important barriers to technology acceptance (Jaschinski & Allouch, 2015; Peek et al., 2014; Zander et al., 2021). This barrier bears several concerns that touch upon all of the dimensions of privacy mentioned above (e.g., Demiris et al., 2009; Garg et al., 2014; Offermann-van Heek et al., 2019). Indeed, these concerns mainly regard the invasion of personal space (physical privacy), permanent surveillance and obtrusiveness (psychological and social privacy), fear of access to, and misuse of, personal information, and data security (information privacy) (Demiris et al., 2009; Garg et al., 2014; Maidhof et al., 2022). Regarding the most important aspect of information privacy, a study by Ziefle et al. (2011) showed that participants question the trustfulness of monitoring devices to ensure legal data transfer and access and prevent technological malfunctioning (e.g., false alarms). However, trusting the system and the ones who receive the data is an important requirement to reach the privacy function of self-protection in a health-monitoring setting, i.e., "protection from the disclosure of sensitive information or information that could cause harm" (McNeill et al., 2017, p. 98). McNeill

et al. (2017) report self-protection as the most commonly mentioned privacy function in their qualitative study on health monitoring. In some cases, self-protection including the protection of personal and sensitive data was mentioned as the only reason why privacy implementations should be included in technology. In line with this, users require to be in control and be self-determined in their decision about which type of data is shared, with whom, and under which conditions (Galambos et al., 2019; Jeffrey et al., 2007; Lorenzen et al., 2011; Maidhof et al., 2022). In health monitoring, the most accepted social contacts who may access data are doctors and family members, while sharing such data with friends is least accepted (Boise et al., 2013; Wilkowska et al., 2021). Furthermore, users want to have control not only over the data flow but also over the technology itself. For instance, the ability to stop or pause the technology from working is mentioned among health-monitoring technology users to increase the sense of control and autonomy (Berridge et al., 2022). Thus, with adequate technological functioning and with suitable features, several privacy functions may be fulfilled and in this way, privacy concerns can be diminished. In general, privacy aspects and related concerns play a crucial role when it comes to deciding for or against adopting monitoring technology (Ehrari et al., 2020; Offermann-van Heek & Ziefle, 2019; Schomakers & Ziefle, 2022). Taken together, among the most important privacy aspects that determine acceptance are the protection and security of data, a self-determined interaction with technological functioning and data, including the ability to supervise who among the social contacts has access to the data.

In the following, we define leading research questions and describe the research design. Subsequently, the main results of the study are presented and discussed.

2.4. Research objectives

According to the above, privacy and trust are crucial determinants of technology acceptance. The extent to which potential users trust a given ambient technology setting, including the aforementioned privacy aspects, possibly impacts technology acceptance. Thus, the overall aim of this study was to consider both trust and privacy as the predictors and/or mediating variables of the acceptance of ambient technology for health-related purposes and to understand the relationships between the variables. To examine the role of these constructs and their interrelations, we formulated the following research questions:

- **RQ1:** How do participants generally perceive and accept using health-related ambient technologies?
- **RQ2:** Which trust conditions have to be fulfilled for using health-related ambient technologies?
- **RQ3:** How do participants perceive the general privacy aspects?
- **RQ4:** How are the research variables interrelated, i.e., how is acceptance of ambient technologies correlated with trust conditions and general privacy perceptions?
- **RQ5:** Which are the strongest predictors for the accepted use of assistive ambient technologies for health-related purposes?

3. Method

In this section, we explain the empirical approach of the conducted study, introducing the research design and the concept of the applied method. Subsequently, we describe the characteristics of our study sample.

We collected the empirical data in the summer of 2022 through an online survey and the data collection was open for participation for around three weeks. It was aimed to reach an equally distributed group of younger, middle-aged, and older German adults who were recruited using interested groups on social networks (i.e., in topics referring to health-related technologies like mHealth and e-Health, AAL, and smart homes) as well as posters with a brief description of the study's topic.

3.1. Research approach

The constructs used for the examination of the research questions addressed in the study are summarized in Figure 1. We used a quantitative research approach in the form of an online survey that operationalized the results of previously conducted qualitative studies exploring the particular topics of trust conditions (Otten & Ziefle, 2022) and general privacy issues in the context of ambient assisted living (Maidhof et al., 2022). The idea was to evaluate and validate these constructs that were considered relevant for the adoption of ambient technologies in private environments such as the own home. To realize the evaluation of the acceptance and anticipated use of ambient technologies as well as to assess the trust conditions and general privacy perceptions, participants were introduced to a descriptive scenario that outlined how the use and functions of health-assisting ambient technology can support them and their caregivers in case of health deterioration. Using the scenario technique aimed at providing a comparable situation for all participants, making them envision themselves in an older age with degradation in health when they can be regularly supported by the ambient technology in their home environments.

As a dependent variable, the study examined the acceptance of ambient technologies for health-related purposes in terms of the perceived usefulness and the intended use of such technologies. Here, also the perceived motives, as well as perceived barriers of use were considered. As independent variables, participants first evaluated trust conditions. After being introduced into the scenario respondents assessed conditions under which they would or would not trust the ambient technology, including statements of trust in data security, health-related trust, and trust in the market readiness and technical soundness of the technology. Second, participants evaluated general aspects of privacy perceptions in this context referring to privacy in terms of data protection, supervision of social contacts as well as self-determination regarding situations, thinking, and behavior.

The participation occurred voluntarily and it took on average less than 15 min to complete the survey. Participants could not proceed with the editing of the survey unless they indicated their informed consent to participate at the onset.

3.2. Design of the online study

In the beginning, participants were provided with a proper background of the study. We outlined the current population aging and the resulting challenges for the health-care system. We also showed that such consequences can be partly mitigated by using

Figure 1. Study design (the main study variables are framed in white in the chart).

ambient technologies to assist individuals in their daily lives. Yet, the increasing need for the use of health-assisting technologies in private environments raises questions about acceptance of, and trust in, such technologies on one side and it provokes considerations about the perception of privacy on the other—all these aspects portraying the main focus of interest in this study. In conclusion of the introducing part, we also informed our participants about the average length of the survey and assured them of a high standard of data protection, which means none of their answers can be referred to them personally.

As presented in Figure 1, the survey consisted of four parts. In the first part, respondents provided information about their demographic data (i.e., age, gender, educational level, and professional background) and indicated their subjectively perceived health condition (ranging from 1="very bad" to 6="very good"). Here, we asked participants to report if they suffer from any—and if so, from which—chronic or acute illness(es) (response alternatives: "yes" vs. "no") and whether they would need and receive nursing care in their day-to-day life (response alternatives: "no" vs. "medical staff" vs. "family members").

In the second part of the questionnaire, we collected data referring to the attitude toward the perceived self-efficacy in technical competence according to Beier (2003) (6 items; $\alpha=.81$) on a six-point Likert-scale ranging from 1 ("I do not agree at all") to 6 ("I fully agree"). We also asked whether our respondents already use health-related technologies or tools, like apps or smartwatches, for monitoring their health parameters and, if so, the type of the used applications (e.g., documentation of vital parameters, nutrition/diet plans, sleep pattern, water/medication intake, etc.).

The third part of the survey represented the heart of the study. We asked participants to envision a situation, in which they are at an advanced age and, besides various health ailments which are typical for that age, they recently experienced coordination difficulties. As moving into a retirement home is not an option, the scenario further describes the participant deciding to install an ambient system at home that assists them in their daily life. The technology for fall prevention, intervention, and control of

the daily routine as well as the analysis of mobility behavior are the decisive assisting functions of the technology. In this scenario, we made it clear that the person concerned is free to decide with whom (e.g., with a family doctor, nursing staff, relatives) and to what extent they share sensitive personal data. After the scenario, participants were asked to evaluate aspects referring to the acceptance of using ambient technologies for health-related reasons like the one that was introduced. Here, respondents firstly assessed statements referring to possible motives (e.g., sense of security, an overview of important body functions, quick notification in case of emergency) and barriers of use (e.g., concerns about surveillance, hacker attack, or data disclosure). In this context, participants also evaluated technology acceptance criteria according to TAM (Davis, 1989), i.e., perceived usefulness (e.g., "I find the collection of my health-related data with the help of the ambient technology useful.") and the intention to use such assistive technologies ("I would like to record my health-related data using the ambient technology."). In addition, after the scenario participants shared their opinions on trust in health-related assistive technology. These items were categorized into three categories *trust in data security* (e.g., "I trust technology only when I can decide who is allowed to view my data."), *trust in health-related use* (e.g., "I trust technology only when it is individually tailored to me [my health]."), and *trust in technical soundness and market readiness* (e.g., "I only trust ambient technology when it has been thoroughly tested."). A detailed list of all acceptance and trust items used in the study can be taken from Tables 1 and 2.

In the fourth part of the survey, we asked participants to evaluate different aspects regarding general perceptions of privacy as this construct is strongly connected with using assistive technologies in private environments. These items were also categorized into three categories referring to the 1) *data protection* (e.g., "The right to determine how, when, and to what extent data about myself are shared with others."), 2) *supervision of social contacts* (e.g., "The ability to withdraw from social interaction."), and 3) *self-determination* (e.g., "The ability to think freely and develop an individual identity.") The privacy statements used in the survey are provided in Table 3.

All acceptance, trust, and privacy items were evaluated on six-point Likert-like agreement scales ranging from 1 ("I do not agree at all") to 6 ("I fully agree") and reached (very) satisfactory internal consistencies of the research variables.

3.3. Sample description

After a quality inspection and data cleaning, data of $N=102$ respondents were taken into consideration for statistical analyses in this study. We addressed potential users of different age and gender as well as individuals with different professional backgrounds and socioeconomic statuses. The sample covered various professional fields, including individuals from the engineering and IT sectors, education and economy as well as health professionals, employers from the social sector, and persons from the artistic sector.

The participants were German adults, ranging in age between 18 and 83 years ($M=35.6$; $SD=9.9$) and the sample was more dominated by female (63.7%; $n=65$) than male participants (34.3%; $n=35$); one individual reported a diverse gender. As the highest educational levels, half of our respondents (50%; $n=51$) reported holding an academic degree (Bachelor's or Master's) and the second largest group indicated their general university entrance qualification (21.6%; $n=22$). Similar was the proportion of respondents holding a vocational baccalaureate diploma (12.7%; $n=13$) or a secondary

school degree (10.8%; $n=11$) as their highest educational qualification; 3 participants (2.9%) reported holding a PhD. Thus, overall our sample was quite well-educated.

Additionally, we collected information regarding health status and experience with the use of health-supporting technical equipment. More than half of the sample indicated good or very good health (58%; $n=59$), 32% of them ($n=33$) marked the response "mostly good" and only round 10% ($n=10$) as mostly bad. From our respondents, 43% reported suffering from a chronic illness ($n=44$), and almost 22.5% ($n=23$) indicated to be currently affected by an acute physical or mental illness. More than half of our sample (53.5%; $n=54$) stated to actively use health-assisting apps or technological tools for documentation of vital parameters (36.6%; $n=37$; e.g., blood pressure, blood sugar), monitoring of physical activities (47.5%; $n=48$; e.g., step count, sport units), control of the sleep-wake rhythm (26.7%; $n=27$), calorie counting/weight loss (22.8%; $n=23$) as well as for diet and nutrition plans (7.8%; $n=8$), monitoring of water intake (7%; $n=7$), and medication intake (4%; $n=4$).

Regarding the attitude towards technological self-efficacy, our analysis revealed that the study participants felt basically good at dealing with technology as the average value was $M=4.5$ ($SD=0.8$) from 6 possible points on the self-efficacy scale.

4. Results

In this section, we present the results of statistical calculations based on the underlying research questions. Regarding statistical analyses, we ensured a satisfying quality of the constructs used in the study, i.e., technology acceptance according to TAM, perceived motives and barriers as well as trust and privacy, by checking the internal consistency of the scales using Cronbach's Alpha ($\alpha \geq .70$). We performed descriptive statistics for the evaluations of acceptance, trust, and privacy statements using means (M) and standard deviations (SD). To examine relationships between the analyzed constructs, we calculated Pearson's product-moment correlation coefficients (ρ). The interpretation of the magnitude of correlation coefficients is guided by Cohen (1988). In addition, we calculated multiple stepwise regression analyses to determine the best predictors for, and the relative contribution of, these research variables to the accepted use of ambient assistive technologies for health reasons. We set the level of statistical significance (p) at 5%.

4.1. Acceptance of ambient technologies

In the first step, we analyzed the general technology acceptance of the use of ambient technologies for health-related purposes RQ1. Participants evaluated acceptance criteria referring to their intended use and perceived usefulness of such health-assisting technology. Results revealed that the majority of our respondents considered the technology useful ($M=4.6$, $SD=1.0$) and would appreciate access to it ($M=4.6$, $SD=1.0$) as it would improve their quality of life in their familiar environment ($M=4.6$, $SD=0.9$). The resulting means for items referring to technology acceptance including perceived motives and barriers are summarized in Table 1.

In addition to the TAM criteria of acceptance, we performed a descriptive analysis of perceived motives and barriers connected to the use of ambient technologies. Here, participants agreed on all the named beneficial arguments, i.e., motives for using ambient technologies that assist them in the health-related context in their home environment. The highest means (≥ 5 of 6 points) resulted for items describing the benefit

Table 1. Descriptive statistics (means and standard deviations) for the acceptance of ambient technologies: perceived motives and barriers as well perceived usefulness and intention to use the technology.

Construct of acceptance	Item description	Mean (SD)
TAM ($\alpha = .91$): Perc. Usefulness	"I consider it useful to record my health-related data with the help of ambient technology."	4.6 (1.0)
	"Ambient technology would improve my quality of life in my familiar environment."	4.6 (0.9)
Intention to use	"I find collecting of my health-related data by ambient technologies useful."	4.4 (1.2)
	"If I have access to ambient technology, I will use it."	4.6 (1.0)
	"I would like to record my health-related data using ambient technologies."	4.3 (1.2)
Perc. motives ($\alpha = .81$)	"I'd like to use amb. technology to collect data because... it gives me a feeling of security."	4.7 (1.2)
	it enables me to live independently in my home."	5.1 (1.0)
	an overview of important bodily functions is useful."	4.7 (1.0)
	in case of emergency, someone will be notified."	5.5 (0.7)
	an emergency call can be triggered even if I am not able to do so."	5.5 (0.7)
	it would give my relatives a secure feeling that I am being cared for."	4.4 (1.3)
	in case of illness this will enable precise, individually tailored diagnoses, therapy or rehabilitation measures to be drawn up."	4.5 (1.1)
Perc. barriers ($\alpha = .88$)	"I am concerned about monitoring by cameras."	4.6 (1.3)
	"I am concerned about hacker attacks."	3.8 (1.6)
	"I consider this system to be an invasion of my privacy."	3.6 (1.5)
	"I am concerned that the system is prone to errors."	4.1 (1.3)
	"I worry to share my personal data through this system."	3.5 (1.5)
	"I am concerned to lose my privacy if I use this system."	3.6 (1.4)
	"I worry about my data being used by unauthorized third parties."	4.1 (1.5)

of notifying someone in case of emergency ($M=5.5$, $SD=0.7$) as well as for the benefit of living independently at home for longer ($M=5.1$, $SD=1.0$). The respondents would also highly enjoy the feeling of security ($M=4.7$, $SD=1.2$) when using ambient technology having at the same time a good overview of their important bodily functions ($M=4.7$, $SD=1.0$).

On the opposite side, the highest barriers to using the technology resulted from items regarding the concern of being monitored by the installed video cameras ($M=4.6$, $SD=1.3$), the system being prone to errors ($M=4.1$, $SD=1.3$), and the worry about access to the sensitive data by unauthorized persons ($M=4.1$, $SD=1.5$). On average, participants reached a neutral opinion regarding sharing their data through the ambient system ($M=3.5$, $SD=1.5$). Opinions regarding barriers were mostly neutral and slightly approving respectively (means ≥ 3.5 of 6 points).

Figure 2 summarizes the general outcomes of acceptance showing the resulting means for the whole constructs. Here, the TAM criteria of acceptance as well as perceived motives for using ambient technology for health clearly dominate the participants' approval over the perceived barriers.

Figure 2. Assessments of the acceptance criteria of using ambient technologies for health-related purposes: TAM, perceived motives, and perceived barriers (N=102).

4.2. Evaluation of trust conditions when using health-related ambient technology

In the next step, the statistical analyses of trust criteria showed that aspects referring to the category *trust in data security* gain the highest approval among the participants (see the top of Figure 3) and are followed by the category *trust in technical soundness and market readiness*. According to the means of single trust items listed in Table 2, our respondents would mostly trust the ambient technology only under the condition that they can decide who is allowed to see, store, and share their personal data (values ≥ 5 of 6 points). Moreover, the perception of being well-informed about the technology ($M=5.0$, $SD=1.0$) and having a good possibility to do so ($M=5.2$, $SD=0.9$) are also crucial conditions for trusting ambient technologies in the health-related context. The respondents clearly required a low error rate ($M=4.7$, $SD=0.9$) and thorough research of the technology beforehand ($M=4.6$, $SD=1.1$). Concerning items referring to the *health-related trust*, participants also agreed on the necessity of a good tailoring to the situation of the person concerned ($M=4.4$, $SD=1.2$) and the relief of her or his caregivers for trusted use of this technology (means ≥ 4).

Table 2. Descriptive statistics (means and standard deviations) resulting for trust items used in the study.

Trust Construct	Item	Mean (SD)
Trust in data security ($\alpha = .92$)	"I only trust the ambient technology... when it is individually tailored to me."	4.9 (1.0)
	"when I can decide who is allowed to view my data."	5.2 (1.0)
	"when my privacy has the highest priority."	5.1 (1.0)
	"when I can decide who is allowed to store my data."	5.2 (1.0)
	"when I can decide who is allowed to share my data."	5.3 (0.9)
Health-related trust ($\alpha = .73$)	"when it improves my health situation."	4.3 (1.2)
	"when it is individually tailored to me."	4.4 (1.2)
	"when it relieves human caregivers."	4.3 (1.2)
	"when it relieves the burden on my relatives."	4.4 (1.2)
Trust in technical soundness and market readiness ($\alpha = .79$)	"when it has a low error rate."	4.7 (0.9)
	"when it is ready for the market."	4.3 (1.1)
	"when it has been thoroughly tested."	4.6 (1.1)
	"when I am well informed about it."	5.0 (1.0)
	"when I can inform myself well about it."	5.2 (0.9)

Figure 3. Overall assessments of the perceptions of privacy (bottom) and trust conditions (top) for using ambient technologies for health-related purposes.

4.3. The assessments of privacy aspects

Our subsequent statistical calculations referred to the general privacy requirements investigated in the context of the study. Figure 3 makes evident that *data protection* poses the greatest requirement for privacy, being followed by equally evaluated *self-determination* and the *supervision of social contacts* (see Figure).

Results on the item level show that participants put a strong emphasis on the control over their personal information and their right to determine how, when, and to what extent this information is shared with third parties (both items $M=5.3$, $SD=0.8$). In terms of privacy, respondents also insisted on their ability to withdraw from social interaction if desired ($M=4.8$, $SD=1.1$), to have control over their social contacts ($M=4.9$, $SD=1.0$), and to determine with whom, and under what circumstances, to share thoughts and feelings or to seek advice from ($M=5.0$, $SD=1.1$). The resulting means for these and other aspects associated with general privacy requirements are summarized in Table 3.

Comparing the descriptive statistics of the overall trust and privacy scales (Figure 3), we conclude that both constructs are considered (very) important in using ambient technologies for health. In the following, we take a closer look at these variables and how they are interrelated. We will further statistically determine which particular trust and privacy aspects are the strongest predictors for the adoption and accepted use of health-assisting ambient systems in private environments.

4.4. Interrelations between the study constructs

To demonstrate the relationships among the main study variables, we performed Pearson product-moment correlation analyses. Figure 4 depicts all significant correlative associations between acceptance, trust, and privacy constructs. There were large correlations between the TAM criteria and the perceived motives and barriers. As in the context of acceptance expected, this outcome shows that perceived usefulness and in-

Table 3. Descriptive statistics (means and standard deviations) resulting for privacy items used in the study.

Privacy Construct	Item	Mean (SD)
Data protection ($\alpha = .75$)	<i>"Privacy means to me... the control over my personal information."</i>	5.3 (0.8)
	<i>the right to determine how, when, and to what extent data about myself are shared with others."</i>	5.3 (0.8)
	<i>my data on my cell phone."</i>	4.8 (1.0)
Supervision of social contacts ($\alpha = .82$)	<i>the ability to withdraw from social interaction."</i>	4.8 (1.1)
	<i>the control I have over my social contacts."</i>	4.9 (1.0)
	<i>the relationships I have with my family."</i>	4.4 (1.3)
	<i>the ability to decide with whom I start a conversation."</i>	4.5 (1.3)
Self- determination ($\alpha = .74$)	<i>situations in which I dissociate myself and I am simply alone."</i>	4.6 (1.3)
	<i>the ability to think freely and develop an individual identity."</i>	4.4 (1.5)
	<i>to determine with whom, and under what circum- stances, to share thoughts and feelings, and to seek advice from."</i>	5.0 (1.1)

tention to use ambient technology are positively correlated with the perceived motives ($\rho=.62, p \leq .001$) and negatively associated with the perceived barriers of use ($\rho=-.45, p \leq .001$).

On the side of trust conditions, a positive association with TAM is given by health-related trust ($\rho=.49, p \leq .001$) and the acceptance moderately correlates with the positive perceptions of the technology's technical soundness and market readiness ($\rho=.28, p \leq .001$). For privacy aspects, small to moderate coefficients resulted between acceptance and self-determination ($\rho=.27, p=.008$) as well as supervision of social contacts ($\rho=.26, p=.009$).

Neither trust in data security ($\rho=.17, p=.096$; n.s.) nor data protection as a privacy requirement ($\rho=-.06, p=.570$; n.s.) were significantly associated with the TAM acceptance criteria. These variables were positively connected with perceived barriers of using ambient technology for health (trust: $\rho=.33, p \leq .001$; privacy: $\rho=.41, p \leq .001$) and only slightly with perceived motives ($\rho=.22, p=.025$). Thus, this outcome showed that trust in data security and data protection in terms of privacy requirements are—if at all—indirectly connected to the accepted use.

The remaining significant correlations between the particular constructs are shown in Figure 4. In the final step of statistical calculations, we will demonstrate which aspects investigated in the study play the most important role in the adoption of health-assisting ambient technology.

4.5. Best predictors for the acceptance of using ambient technologies

We finally provide evidence about which of the examined constructs are the best predictors for the accepted use of ambient technology for health. To answer the underlying research question (RQ5) and to understand the role of trust and privacy requirements for acceptance of ambient technology, a stepwise linear regression analysis was conducted. For that purpose, all predictors (i.e., perceived motives and barriers, trust in data security, health-related trust, trust in technical soundness and market readiness as well as privacy in terms of data protection, supervision of social contacts, and self-determination) were entered into the equation simultaneously to show how much unique variance is explained by construct variables included into the model in the de-

Figure 4. Correlations between the study variables: i. technology acceptance (TAM, perceived motives, perceived barriers), ii. trust conditions (data security, health-related, technical soundness), and iii. privacy requirements (data protection, supervision of social contacts, self-determination) for using ambient technologies for health [$**p \leq .01$, $*p \leq .05$].

pendent variable, i.e., TAM-based acceptance. The regression model is given in Table 4 and the results of the regression analysis are discussed below.

Table 4. Results of the standard multiple regression analysis for the TAM-based acceptance of the use of ambient technology in a private home ($N=102$; $**p \leq .001$, $*p \leq .01$; VIF=variance inflation factor $\div 10$)

Predictors	Adj. R^2	β	t	VIF	ANOVA
Perceived motives	61.7%	.40	5.53**	1.31	$F(5,96)=31.9$,
Perceived barriers		-.43	-6.10**	1.25	$p \leq .001$
Privacy: Supervision of social contacts		.10	1.37	1.24	
Trust: Technical soundness		.21	2.82*	1.32	
Health-related trust		.20	2.73*	1.36	

For the TAM-based acceptance, the final regression model contained five predictors. The model was statistically significant [$F(5,96)=31.9$, $p \leq .001$] and accounted for approximately 62% of the variance ($R^2=.637$; adjusted $R^2=.617$). Perceived motives ($\beta=.40$) and barriers ($\beta=-.42$) received the strongest weights in the model, and were followed by health-related trust ($\beta=.20$) and the trust condition of a technical soundness/market readiness of the technology ($\beta=.21$). Thus, for this model the variables perceived motives [$t(96)=5.53$, $p \leq 0.001$], barriers [$t(96)=-6.1$, $p \leq 0.001$] as well as health-related trust [$t(96)=2.73$, $p=0.008$] and trust in technical soundness [$t(96)=2.82$, $p=0.006$] are all significant predictors of the acceptance of ambient technologies. In contrast, supervision of social contacts as an aspect of general privacy [$t(96)=1.37$, n.s.] did not make a significant contribution to the prediction of acceptance in terms of perceived usefulness and intention to use ambient technology. The VIF and tolerance values suggest no multicollinearity within the present data.

5. Discussion

The aim of this study was to deepen knowledge about the opinions of potential users and their intended use of ambient technologies assisting them in everyday life in health-related activities and measures. Particular attention was directed to the role of trust and privacy issues in the accepted use of such ambient technologies. In an empirical approach, we conducted a quantitative online study and examined how the different aspects of trust in technology and general privacy perceptions are connected with the technology acceptance and intended use of ambient technologies for health. In the following, we first summarize the key results of the study discussing them on the basis of the previously established research questions. Secondly, we look at what limitations need to be considered in the interpretation and application of the conclusions drawn from this study, and which further aspects are important in future research in this area.

5.1. Key study outcomes and their relevance in the field

Taking RQ1 into account, our study validated the findings of other studies in this area (e.g., Jaschinski & Allouch, 2019; Offermann-van Heek et al., 2019; Wilkowska et al., 2022): Participants generally accept and are willing to use ambient technology for health-related purposes acknowledging the technology’s usefulness in their everyday life. According to the results numerous advantages and motives, on which participants consistently agreed, outweigh the perceived barriers. Participants appreciate the feeling of security and the benefit of living independently at home for longer when using ambient technology. They are also motivated to use the technology by the possibility of notifying others in case of emergency and they enjoy having a regular overview of their body parameters. Nevertheless, the perceived barriers are not to be overlooked either. The concerns of being monitored by video cameras, system errors, and the worry about the misuse of sensitive data still pose the greatest barriers to the adoption of ambient technology, indicating that potential users can also be hesitant in the acceptance of the technology; similar results have been found in previous research in the rehabilitation context (Choukou et al., 2021).

Following that, the question arises of which trust conditions have to be fulfilled for the successful adoption of assistive ambient technologies (RQ2). Our study revealed that data security, i.e., clear regulations about who and when is allowed to view, share, and store sensible health-related data, is considered to be most relevant among the trust conditions. This result aligns with prior research that showed trust having a significant impact on e-commerce usage (McCloskey, 2006) or internet banking adoption (Kesharwani & Singh Bisht, 2012). In the study, the second-ranked construct was technical soundness, i.e., a low error rate, along with market readiness, i.e., thorough previous testing and available information about the technology. The relevance of this trust aspect likewise confirms the results of a previous study, where trustworthiness in terms of reliability and a well-thought-out functionality of the technology were identified as the relevant trust conditions of eHealth technology (Wilkowska & Ziefle, 2019). Furthermore, trust in technology results revealed a high importance of tailoring the particular applications to the individual health situation and needs of the user(s). Even if the health-related trust resulted to be slightly less pronounced than the other trust aspects of the study, the outcomes suggest that users clearly expect from the ambient technology an improvement of their health situation at large, relieving at the

same time the burden on relatives and/or the support of other caregivers.

The demand for data protection is also directly reflected in the results on how users perceive the general privacy aspects (RQ3). Here, our study respondents assigned the highest attention to the control over personal information and their right to determine how, when, and to what extent their data are shared with others. As the concept was measured on a rather general level, these perceptions refer to the participants' states of mind about privacy without specific relations to the technology. It is therefore interesting that the findings on general privacy perceptions align with previous research that emphasizes the importance of privacy preservation when using ambient technologies and systems (e.g., Psychoula et al., 2018; Wilkowska et al., 2020, 2022). Our study results additionally revealed that the supervision of social contacts as well as the construct of self-determination on situations and the amount of information that is exchanged pose considerable privacy requirements in the accepted use of ambient technologies in health-related issues, again corroborating previous research (Lorenzen et al., 2011).

The presented results substantiate empirical evidence that the concepts of trust and privacy rank highly in terms of the accepted use of health-related assistive technology (Dhagarra, 2020). This finding is hardly surprising since allowing the technology for health assistance requires more than the pure availability of such. However, the constructs are not to be considered separate entities. Rather, the question emerges of how these constructs are interrelated (RQ4). Our analysis revealed that trust conditions and privacy requirements are moderate to strongly connected either directly to acceptance, i.e., perceived usefulness and intended use of ambient technology, or indirectly via perceived motives and barriers. Besides, perceptions of factors that motivate and/or hinder the adoption of technology are strongly—positively or negatively—related to the examined technology acceptance criteria. Meanwhile, the sub-constructs of trust and privacy are moderately interrelated (for details see Section 4.4). Yet, one somehow surprising result represents the non-existent relationship between acceptance and the variables of trust in data security and data protection as a privacy requirement. Data security is usually one of the most important aspects of privacy which impacts technology adoption (McNeill et al., 2017; Smith et al., 2011) however, here, these variables were not directly connected with technology acceptance but showed correlations with perceived motives and barriers, whereby positive moderate coefficients resulted especially for the perceived barriers. This finding suggests that data security and protection—at least as it is handled in Germany—are rather perceived as obstructing the path to the adoption of ambient technologies in private environments. It remains to consider that privacy was assessed on a rather general level with no specific relation to the ambient technology, which might be simply reflected in the result. However, the privacy of data, control over social contacts, and self-determination are important factors in normal daily life, and depending on how these single, generally valid, factors are evaluated and viewed, they may either represent a barrier or a motive for any sort of context, as is also the case for ambient technologies.

But which of the study constructs predicts the accepted use of assistive technology for health-related purposes best? (RQ5) According to the results of the regression analyses, besides the perceived motives and barriers, health-related trust and trust in technical reliability and market readiness are the strongest predictors for acceptable technology use and significantly contribute to the explanation of the variance. The privacy aspect referring to the supervision of social contacts was also included in the model, even though its impact was rather small. All these predictors accounted for a large proportion of the variance (nearly 62%) for accepted ambient technology use.

As opposed to that, the sub-constructs data security and data protection as well as self-determination in terms of general privacy were not decisive for acceptance and were excluded from the regression model. With this result, we can state that trust in the effectiveness or support of the ambient technology has a greater contribution to the successful adoption of the technology than the demands regarding general privacy. These results are largely consistent with new research on the direct predictors of patients' behavior to accept technology in availing healthcare services (Dhagarra, 2020).

Considering the described finding, we can conclude that trust conditions and perceptions of privacy as presented in the study are significantly connected with the acceptance of using health-assistive ambient technologies. These findings corroborate previous research on acceptance of ambient systems: On the basis of preceding qualitative studies (Maidhof et al., 2022; Otten & Ziefle, 2022) exploring which requirements potential users of such systems have, relevant trust conditions and demands referring to privacy could be identified and the results were validated within this quantitative survey study.

5.2. Limitations and future research

Despite the valuable insights into factors that play a crucial role in the acceptance and successful implementation of ambient technologies for health purposes, there are certain reservations that need to be considered in the interpretation of the findings and the transfer of their validity.

With regard to the sample of the study, due to a high dropout rate and after data quality check only 64% of the completed questionnaires were eligible for statistical analyses. Thus, the sample size was quite small. In addition, the participants were on average quite young with a higher proportion of females and indicated quite high education levels. Given the scores on attitude towards technological self-efficacy, we can therefore assume that many of our respondents had a comparably good understanding of, and technical skills referring to, ambient technologies. However, since high affinity and trouble-free dealing with technology cannot be assumed for older and mostly less savvy technology users, the results cannot be transferred without further ado to the whole population. Hence, in future studies, greater focus should be placed on validating the results with a higher number of more gender-balanced older participants with less technical experience as they are the actual target group for using health-assistive technologies that support their autonomous living. An international study that considers varying cultural peculiarities (e.g., varying healthcare systems, caregiver models, etc.) could bring additional insights into this matter. The research should consider specific user groups (e.g., healthy persons, individuals with chronic conditions or disabilities, their caregivers, etc.) and investigate their specific requirements: The demands and necessities of individuals who let themselves be assisted by ambient technology for preventive purposes or to gain a better physical fitness will probably significantly vary from users who strive to rehabilitate their previous skills or abilities (e.g., after stroke) or to cope with their long-term disability/chronic illness in everyday life.

Furthermore, constructs of trust and privacy were measured not on the same levels. Trust was conceptualized as an AAL context-specific belief or expectancy whereas privacy was conceptualized as a rather generic state of mind, disposition, or assertion of control consisting of several dimensions. However, opposing a multi-dimensional and

specific trust construct with a rather generic multi-dimensional privacy construct was still reasonable as the privacy construct referred to general daily life, which, different from the trust construct, is a sufficient enough reference to be measured for privacy. For instance, data security (i.e., informational privacy) or invasion of personal space (i.e., physical privacy) are generally important aspects of daily life, regardless of technology or setting. Indeed, the assessed generic privacy dispositions or states of mind still significantly influenced technology constructs in this study. Nonetheless, privacy has been reported to be contextual (Nissenbaum, 2009) and future studies should investigate the interplay of technology-specific privacy and trust using constructs on the same level.

Another weak point of the study refers to the fact that findings are based on evaluations resulting from a scenario in which participants solely envisioned the use of ambient technology. This anticipated use of the technology can considerably vary from the real use and hands-on studies are needed for findings on trust and privacy requirements in the context of using ambient technologies that are at most close to reality.

6. Conclusion

This empirical study examined the importance of trust conditions and general privacy perceptions in an accepted use of ambient technologies for health-related purposes using an online survey as a method. Findings suggest that potential users accept and appreciate benefits resulting from the assistance of ambient technologies under consideration of relevant trust conditions and general privacy requirements, which are significantly interrelated. Nevertheless, perceived barriers can overshadow the adoption. According to our results, besides perceived motives and barriers, meeting the trust conditions is decisive for the prediction of accepted technology use. Data security and protection are thereby perceived as indispensable.

This paper contributes to a user-driven approach in the research of ambient technologies in private and institutional environments providing important implications for researchers, developers, and policymakers in the development and design of such. Findings enable a better understanding of how users accept ambient technology for health, including considerations on trust and privacy, and provide insight into how this technology may be used, disused, or misused. The results are both a good baseline to guide future research efforts as well as a validation of previous research. Finally, this study aids the design of ambient technologies from a user perspective and provides ideas for user-centered policy directions in this domain.

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Notes on contributors

Conceptualization, W.W., S.O. and C.M.; methodology, W.W. and S.O.; validation, W.W., S.O. and C.M.; formal analysis, W.W.; investigation, W.W. and S.O.; resources W.W., S.O. and C.M.; data curation, W.W.; writing—original draft preparation, W.W., S.O. and C.M.; writing—review and editing, W.W., S.O. and C.M.; visualization, W.W.; project administration, M.Z.; funding acquisition, M.Z. All authors have read and agreed to the published version of the manuscript.

Notes

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